

IMMUNOGLOBULIN LEVELS IN NEWBORNS DEPENDING ON THE TYPE OF NUTRITION

Abdieva Nargiza Rustamovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15342106>

Abstract: The article is devoted to the development of a new method for diagnosing disorders of the immuno-metabolic status in premature newborns, which is very important for improving the quality of neonatology care and the degree of survival of underweight children. Timely assessment of the immune status and metabolic changes helps to increase the effectiveness of treatment, prevent critical conditions in premature newborns and reduce the frequency of neonatal mortality.

Keywords: newborns, immunity, premature babies, metabolism, cytokines.

Introduction.

The role of the immune system in early postnatal adaptation is extremely important. During the transition from sterile conditions of intrauterine development to conditions of increased antigenic load, the state of various parts of the immune system inevitably changes [3].

Currently, it has been proven to increase the production of pro-inflammatory interleukins in the mother's body when starting labor. In addition, cytokines are one of the leading mechanisms in protecting a newborn child during early adaptation. IL-6 is one of the main regulators of the immune response and hematopoiesis. In addition, it acts as a mediator of protective processes against infection and tissue damage. Premature birth is associated with high IL-6 synthesis [1].

In newborns with intrauterine infection, the target organs are not only the epithelial cells of the mucous membranes and skin, the immune system, but also the vascular endothelium, neurons and neuroglia containing stocks of stem cells. Insufficient activity of monocyte macrophages worsens the barrier function of organs with additional damage to neurons, myocardiocytes, hepatocytes and other cells by persistent infections and the development of a systemic inflammatory reaction of mesenchymal tissues [2,5].

It is known that the functional state of the central nervous system at birth plays an important role in ensuring the mechanisms of subsequent normophysiological development of the child. At the same time, structural damage to the central nervous system can lead to a breakdown of adaptation mechanisms during the transition from intrauterine to extrauterine existence, a change in the homeostatic parameters of the internal environment of the newborn's body and, on this basis, cause secondary diseases or complicate the course of an existing pathology [7]. Despite the large number of adverse factors that can simultaneously affect the fetus, their effect on the brain is not specific and is mainly associated with perinatal hypoxia, accompanied by hemodynamic and metabolic disorders [2,5].

The purpose of the research: development of a method for diagnosing disorders of the immuno-metabolic status in premature newborns

Materials and methods of research:

The study included 125 newborns divided into 3 groups:

The first control group consisted of 45 healthy newborns who were exclusively breastfed, the 2nd main group consisted of 40 newborns with extremely low (ELBW) and very low body weight (VLBW) who were on parenteral nutrition with a minimum amount of expressed breast milk (EBM), 3- the main group consisted of 40 newborns with VLBW and low body weight (LBW), who were on a mixed enteral diet, received 70% of native expressed breast milk and 30% of breast milk substitutes (BMS) Pre-NAN (Nestle, Switzerland),

Gestational age, birth weight, the decrease in the initial weight and the age of its recovery, the presence of adverse perinatal factors, and the treatment performed did not differ between the groups of children, which indicated their homogeneity.

Among the selected groups, clinical indicators were obtained by comparing each of the studied groups with the control group according to the Student's t-criterion and the z-criterion for comparing percentages. The results are presented in the form of percentages in the group structure, arithmetic averages (M), standard deviations (σ), average errors (m). Statistical processing of the data obtained was performed using the standard Excel 7.0 analysis package and the Statistika 6.0 software package. The reliability of quantitative indicators, which do not differ in variance, was assessed using the Student's parametric t-test. The confidence level accepted for the t-test $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results and discussion.

Interesting data were obtained regarding the level of IgA, the highest indicator was observed in group 2 in newborns with ELBW was determined in trace amounts of 0.42-0.15 g/l, which is 2.8 times less than in healthy children. In 18 (40%) newborns, the immunoglobulin level was less than 0.1 g/l, which corresponds to the literature data that the synthesis of IgA by the fetus in trace amounts is possible normally from the 30th week of gestation, and with antigenic stimulation by infectious agents – starting from the 13th–14th weeks of intrauterine development. In group 3, in premature newborns with VLBW and LBW, the concentration of IgA was (2.26-0.09g/l), on the contrary, higher than in healthy children (1.19-0.07g/l). A twofold increase in IgA in premature infants of group 3 relative to control values is associated with the presence of a gastric probe as an invasive factor stimulating the synthesis of immunoglobulin by the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract and enteral nutrition in newborns.

Figure 1. Serum immunoglobulin A and G levels in newborns

It is believed that the development of infectious diseases is based on the relative immaturity of the immune system of a premature baby. This applies to systemic (humoral and cellular) and local immunity. The main form of the immunological response to the introduction of genetically foreign substances and infection is the formation of non-specific protective factors. Humoral protection factors of a premature baby are mainly represented by maternal antibodies, however, the greatest intake of immunoglobulin G (IgG) through the placenta occurs after 34 weeks of gestation. Immunoglobulins of classes A and M are practically absent in the body of a premature baby

Conclusions:

A twofold increase in IgA was determined in premature newborns with VLBW and ELBW who were on enteral nutrition relative to control values, and in the group with ELBW, IgA was determined in trace amounts. Significantly low serum IgG concentrations indicated morphological immaturity of the immune system correlating with the gestational age of the newborn.

References:

Используемая литература:

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Donders G. Aerobic vaginitis in pregnancy/G. Donders, G. Bellen, D. Rezeberga//Br.J. Obstet. Gynaecol. – 2017. – N 118 (10). – P. 1163–1170.
2. Fang C.T., Lai S.Y., Yi W.C., Hsueh P.R., Liu K.L., Chang S.C. Klebsiella pneumoniae Genotype K1: An Emerging Pathogen That Causes Septic Ocular or Central Nervous System Complications from Pyogenic Liver Abscess. Clinical Infectious Diseases, 2017, Vol. 45, pp. 284-293.
3. Morita H., Arae K., Ohno T., Kajiwara N., Oboki K., Matsuda A., Suto H., Okumura K., Sudo K., Takahashi T., Matsumoto K., Nakae S. ST2 Requires Th2-, but Not Th17-, Type Airway

Inflammation in Epicutaneously AntigenSensitized Mice. *Allergology International*, 2022, Vol. 61, pp. 265-273.

4. Nandyal R. Update on group B streptococcal infections: perinatal and neonatal periods.//*J. Perinat.Neonatal. Nurs.* – 2018. – N22 (3). – P. 230–237.

5. Nseir S., Ader F., Marquette C.H. Nosocomial tracheobronchitis. *Curr. Opin. Infect. Dis.*, 2019, Vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 148-153.

6. Palmer L.B., Smaldone G.C., Chen J.J., Baram D., Duan T., Monteforte M., Varela M., Tempone A.K., O’Riordan T., Daroowalla F., Richman P. Aerosolized antibiotics and ventilator-associated tracheobronchitis in the intensive care unit. *Crit. Care Med.*, 2018, Vol. 36, no. 7.

7. Romero R. The role of inflammation and infection in preterm birth/R. Romero, J. Espinoza, L.F. Goncalves//*Semin. Reprod. Med.* – 2017. – N 25 (1). – P. 21–39.

8. Shinkai H., Tanaka M., Morozumi T., Eguchi-Ogawa T., Okumura N., Muneta Y., Awata T., Uenishi H. Biased distribution of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in porcine Toll-like receptor 1 (TLR1), TLR2, TLR4, TLR5 and TLR6 genes. *Immunogenetics*, 2016, Vol. 58, pp. 324-330.

